

Trialkoxysilane Exchange: Scope, Mechanism, Cryptates and pH-Response

Selina Hollstein, Philipp Erdmann⁺, Andreas Ulmer⁺, Henrik Löw, Lutz Greb,^{*} and Max von Delius^{*}

Abstract: The dynamic covalent chemistry (DCvC) of the Si–O bond holds unique opportunities, but has rarely been employed to assemble discrete molecular architectures. This may be due to the harsh conditions required to initiate exchange reactions at silicon in aprotic solvents. Herein, we provide a comprehensive experimental and computational account on the reaction of trialkoxysilanes with alcohols and identify mild conditions for rapid exchange in aprotic solvents. Substituent, solvent and salt effects are uncovered, understood and exploited for the construction of sila-orthoester cryptates. A sharp, divergent pH-response of the obtained cages renders this substance class attractive for future applications well beyond host-guest chemistry, for instance, in drug delivery.

Introduction

Dynamic covalent chemistry (DCvC) as a research field that seeks to study and utilize reversible covalent bonds has been enabling advances in, e.g., bioconjugation,^[1–9] supramolecular chemistry^[10–21] and organic materials.^[22–35] Over the last two decades, the DCvC toolbox has been systematically extended from imines, olefins, thioesters, disulfides, hydrazones and boronic esters,^[36,37] to diselenides,^[38,39] tetrazines,^[40,41] triazines,^[42,43] (hemi)aminals,^[44,45] dithioacetals,^[46,47] orthoesters,^[48,49] thioorthoesters,^[50] amidines,^[51,52] alkynes,^[53,54] ureas,^[55] azines^[56] and even amides.^[57–59] Increasingly, the key to unlock the potential of “new” dynamic covalent bonds is to

identify reaction conditions that are suitably mild to allow constitutional exchange on yet thermodynamically robust connections.

In the past six years, the reversible nature of Si–O bonds has been exploited to achieve different ends. For instance, Thomas and colleagues were able to prepare a covalent organic framework that featured hexacoordinate silicon nodes.^[60] Guan described vitrimers based on silyl ethers (herein best understood as monoalkoxysilanes) that exhibited adaptive behavior (Figure 1a, left).^[61] The group of von Hähnisch reported elegant syntheses of dialkoxysilane analogues of cryptands and crown ethers,^[62–64] which in the most recent work was facilitated by a template effect.^[63] Earlier this year, Johnson made use of mild reaction conditions to facilitate the dynamic covalent synthesis of thermosets based on dialkoxysilanes (Figure 1a, center)^[65] and one of us used Si–O bond metathesis to prepare large, catechol-bridged macrocycles under thermodynamic control (Figure 1a, right).^[66] While these and other reports highlight the value of the dynamic Si–O bond for polymers and macrocycles,^[67–70] the exploitation of trialkoxysilanes in host-guest chemistry is elusive.

Numerous earlier studies focused on the alcoholysis of alkoxy silanes, using a large excess of the exchanging reagent.^[71–74] Unfortunately, such solvolytic conditions exclude controlled stoichiometries required for the assembly of well-defined molecular architectures, while a mild Si–OR/H–OR exchange under non-solvolytic conditions has not yet

[*] S. Hollstein, A. Ulmer,⁺ Dr. H. Löw, Prof. Dr. M. von Delius
 Institute of Organic Chemistry, Ulm University
 Albert-Einstein-Allee 11, 89081 Ulm (Germany)
 E-mail: max.vondelius@uni-ulm.de

P. Erdmann,⁺ Prof. Dr. L. Greb
 Anorganisch-Chemisches Institut, Ruprecht-Karls-Universität, Heidelberg
 Im Neuenheimer Feld 270, 69120 Heidelberg (Germany)
 E-mail: greb@uni-heidelberg.de

[⁺] These authors contributed equally to this work.

© 2023 The Authors. Angewandte Chemie International Edition published by Wiley-VCH GmbH. This is an open access article under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

a) dynamic covalent Si–O exchange

b) this work

Figure 1. Scope of this study in the context of previous work on dynamic covalent Si–O chemistry.

been established. Herein, we report a comprehensive experimental and computational study on the DCvC of trialkoxysilanes with stoichiometric amounts of alcohols in aprotic solvents. By combining our two groups' experience on silicon esters, silicate anions and macrocycles^[66,75–77] and orthoester cryptates,^[78–82] we gain insights into the exchange mechanism and leverage these insights for identifying mild reaction conditions that ultimately allow the synthesis of a new class of supramolecular hosts. Valuable trends on solvent and salt additives are identified and manifest the ubiquitous Si–O bond as a tool for all fields making use of DCvC.

Results and Discussion

Trialkoxysilane exchange: substituent effects

Being aware that only the identification of suitably mild reaction conditions can make trialkoxysilane exchange a versatile tool for DCvC, we began this study with a broad look at the reactivity of this compound class. To investigate the influence of substituents at the Si-bridgehead, we chose a set of six commercially available (R = –H, –CH₃, –CH₂Cl, –C₆H₅, –C₆F₅, –^tBu) and one synthesized (R = –mesityl) trimethoxysilanes. The trimethoxysilanes **A**₃ were treated with three equivalents of ethanol **B** under standardized reaction conditions (room temperature, 50 mM in CDCl₃). The reaction progress was monitored for up to 24 hours by ¹H NMR spectroscopy to determine the equilibration time *t*. In the absence of a catalyst, no exchange was observed for most substrates. The only exception was the smallest trimethoxysilane (R = –H), which showed ¹H NMR signals indicative of exchange even in the absence of added acid (Figure S39).^[83] When studying acid catalysts, we quickly noticed that the vast reactivity differences between the trialkoxysilanes made it necessary to vary both the amount and the type of acid to achieve equilibration within 24 hours. In Table 1, the studied trialkoxysilanes are ordered from

most reactive to most inert (from top to bottom). While trimethoxysilane (R = –H, Table 1, entry 1) equilibrated with ethanol within 40 min using only 10 mol % trifluoroacetic acid (TFA), four silanes (R = –C₆H₅, –mesityl, –C₆F₅, –^tBu) did not reach equilibrium within 24 h in the presence of 100 mol % TFA (Figure S19, S21, S23 and S25).

For these bulkier substituents we observed equilibration times of less than four hours only when employing the stronger trifluoromethane sulfonic acid (TfOH; 1–50 mol %, Table 1). Notably, *tert*-butyltrimethoxysilane (R = –^tBu, entry 7) required by far the harshest reaction conditions (50 mol % TfOH), indicating that steric demand is a major contributor to the observed trends. When trying to rationalize these results with free energy relationships (LFER), we realized that both Taft's "steric parameter" $E_s^{[84]}$ and the conformational energies (*A* values),^[85] which are both included in Table 1, correlate relatively well with the observed reactivity. Taken together, the E_s metric and *A* values should therefore be helpful tools to roughly predict the reactivity of the many commercially available trialkoxysilanes (currently ca. 80 trialkoxysilanes available from Sigma Aldrich, Germany). Interestingly, we had previously found that Taft's "polar parameter" (σ^*) is the best metric to predict the reactivity of orthoesters, which are the carbon analogues of trialkoxysilanes.^[86] This observed divergence between orthoesters (electronic effects dominate) and trialkoxysilanes (steric effects dominate) can be explained by the different reaction mechanisms. Orthoester exchange proceeds via an oxonium ion intermediate,^[79] which is why electronic effects have a more pronounced effect on the rate of exchange (or hydrolysis). In contrast, trialkoxysilane exchange should proceed in an associative manner through the formation of penta-coordinated intermediates (see also below),^[87,88] which is why the steric demand of substituents generally outweighs electronic effects. If steric differences are subtle, as in the two substituents –C₆H₅ and –C₆F₅ (Table 1, entries 4 and 6), the effect of the –C₆F₅ group is to diminish reactivity, which stands in contrast to the expectation that an electron-withdrawing group should increase

Table 1: Kinetics and scope of acid-induced trialkoxysilane exchange.^[a]

entry	acid	R	<i>t</i> ^[b] [min]	product ratio (A ₃ : A _{2B:AB₂:B₃)}	Taft $-E_s^{[84]}$	<i>A</i> values [kcal/mol] ^[85]
1	10% TFA	–H	40	11:32:37:20	0.00	0.0
2	100% TFA	–CH ₃	430	12:32:32:24	1.24	1.7
3	100% TFA	–CH ₂ Cl	940	12:30:29:29	1.48	n. a.
4	1% TfOH	–C ₆ H ₅	60	13:35:33:19	3.79	2.8
5	1% TfOH	–mesityl	70	16:36:33:15	n. a.	n. a.
6	5% TfOH	–C ₆ F ₅	250	11:35:34:20	n. a.	n. a.
7	50% TfOH	– ^t Bu	210	15:36:31:18	2.78	4.7–4.8

[a] Reaction conditions: silane (**A**₃, 37.5 μmol, 1.0 equiv), ethanol (**B**, 112.5 μmol, 3.0 equiv), internal NMR standard toluene (9.41 μmol) and acid catalyst (1 to 100 mol %) were added to the reaction vessel from stock solutions. CDCl₃ was added to obtain a total volume of 750 μL. The reaction was monitored by ¹H NMR spectroscopy at room temperature. [b] *t*: equilibration time, defined as data point when 99% conversion to plateau-level of exchange was exceeded for the first time. Estimated error: ±20%. n. a. = not available.

electrophilicity at the central Si atom and therefore increase reactivity. In general, trialkoxysilanes require larger amounts of acid catalyst or stronger acids than orthoesters to enable efficient exchange (at least in the absence of salt additives, see below).^[86]

Considering thermodynamics rather than kinetics, it is noteworthy that the observed product ratios at equilibrium are in favor of a higher –OEt content in the product. Again, this differs from our observations made with orthoester exchange, in which case the smaller –OMe residues always outweighed the larger –OEt residues.^[86] We propose that this finding can be rationalized by subtle London dispersion between neighboring ethoxy groups^[89] and/or the different solvation energies of ethanol and methanol in aprotic medium.

Computational studies on the role of the acid and observation of key Si–OC(O)CF₃ intermediates

To gain insights into the mechanism, DFT studies were performed (RI-DSD-PBEP86-D3BJ/ma-def2-QZVPP) for the “direct” and TFA-mediated methanol self-exchange reaction. Since only stoichiometric amounts of alcohol were used in the experiments, the involvement of more than one alcohol in higher order transition structures, as often proposed under solvolytic conditions,^[90,91] was not considered. Table 2 reports the transition state free energies (in vacuum and solvation corrected by COSMO-RS(CHCl₃)) for the direct methanol exchange, TFA exchange, and methanol exchange at a R–Si(OMe)₂(TFA) intermediate. First, it becomes evident that the barriers for the direct methanol exchange are too high to be surpassed under ambient conditions (Table 2, column 2, averaged $\Delta G^{\ddagger}_{\text{solv}} = 148 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$), in agreement with the experimental observation that the non-catalyzed process is unfeasible. However, both the exchange of TFA at R–Si(OMe)₃ (Table 2, column 4) and the subsequent MeOH exchange at the R–Si(OMe)₂(TFA) intermediate (Table 2, column 6) feature

Table 2: Computed Gibbs reaction barriers for the “direct” MeOH exchange, the TFA exchange and the MeOH exchange at the RSi(OMe)₂(TFA) intermediate, without and with solvation correction.

R	Direct MeOH exchange		TFA exchange		MeOH exchange at R–Si(OMe) ₂ (TFA)	
	ΔG^{\ddagger}	$\Delta G_{\text{solv}}^{\ddagger}$	ΔG^{\ddagger}	$\Delta G_{\text{solv}}^{\ddagger}$	ΔG^{\ddagger}	$\Delta G_{\text{solv}}^{\ddagger}$
–H	138	140	109	109	114	113
–CH ₃	154	160	120	114	127	128
– ^t Bu	165	172	126	122	127	129
–C ₆ H ₅	139	146	121	121	117	120
–C ₆ F ₅	122	129	133	141	108	110

Free energies are given in kJ mol^{-1} , obtained at the RI-DSD-PBEP86(D3BJ)/ma-def2-QZVPP//PBEh-3c/def2-mSVP level of theory. $\Delta G_{\text{solv}}^{\ddagger}$ values corrected for solvation by COSMO-RS model in CHCl₃.

lower barriers (averaged $\Delta G^{\ddagger}_{\text{solv}} = 123/118 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ respectively). Interestingly, both exchange reactions proceed preferentially via 4-membered ring O–H/Si–O bond metathesis instead of a 6-membered transition state (see Table S5). This contrasts the recent study by Johnson on dialkoxysilanes and carboxylic acids, wherein the 6-membered TS was found as preferred.^[65] A similar 4-membered cyclic transition state was recently postulated to be involved in transimination reactions.^[92,93] The barriers for the direct methanol exchange become higher upon solvation correction (Table 2, column 3), whereas an effective barrier lowering is observed for the TFA-mediated process (Table 2, column 4, see below *for further discussion*). Analyzing the exchange barriers for different substituents reveals that for the direct process, the more electron-rich substituents (R = –Me/–^tBu) feature higher barriers, whereas for the TFA-mediated process, the electron-poor substituent (R = –C₆F₅) shows the highest barrier. Accordingly, the DFT calculations attribute the unexpected difference between R = –C₆H₅ and –C₆F₅ to solvation (Table 1, entries 4 and 6). Notably, the different response to solvent polarity for the direct vs. TFA-mediated exchange pathways should allow a reversal in reaction rates that might open opportunities in synthesis, systems chemistry or responsive materials.

Since our computational results indicated that TFA plays an immediate role, we attempted to identify corresponding intermediates. Mixtures of Ph–Si(OMe)₃ with varying amounts of TFA in CDCl₃ were analyzed by heteronuclear and multidimensional NMR spectroscopy (Figure 2). Adding 0.5 or 1.0 equiv of TFA caused the formation of a new species with a ²⁹Si NMR chemical shift of –62.3 ppm, while additional species at –68.6 and –77.4 ppm increasingly formed with 2.0 and 3.0 equiv of TFA. All these silicon species revealed couplings to C₆H₅-residues by ¹H–²⁹Si HMBC NMR spectroscopy, and no formation of C₆H₆ could be observed, ruling out alternative products from acid induced cleavage of the Si–C bond.^[94,95] ¹H and ¹⁹F NMR spectra, and a cross-peak in the ¹H–¹⁹F HOESY NMR spectrum between CF₃ fluorine nuclei and phenyl protons were in line with the formation of Ph–Si(OMe)_{3–m}(TFA)_m adducts, confirming the results from the computational studies. In contrast, when TfOH is used in the same type of experiment, only one type of adduct is observed (^tBu–Si(OMe)₂(TfOH)) (Figure S38).

Figure 2: Reaction of Ph–Si(OMe)₃ with varying amounts of TFA and reaction products as observed by ²⁹Si NMR spectroscopy.

Identifying mild reaction conditions

Having understood the rate-enhancing effect of TFA in chloroform, we wondered whether even milder reaction conditions could be identified. As a substrate with relatively low reactivity, we chose phenyltrimethoxysilane ($R = -C_6H_5$) and studied its exchange with ethanol in the presence of 100 mol % TFA in a variety of aprotic solvents. In chloroform, phenyltrimethoxysilane had required the stronger acid TfOH to reach equilibrium within one hour, so the purpose of these experiments was to identify solvents that facilitate satisfying exchange already with the milder acid TFA. As shown in Figure 3, we chose a broad range of solvents featuring a wide range of polarity (benzene, chloroform, tetrahydrofuran (THF), dichloromethane (DCM), acetonitrile, *N,N'*-dimethylformamide (DMF), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO)), and two examples of basic solvents (pyridine and hexamethylphosphoric triamide (HMPA)).

When inspecting the kinetic profiles of these reactions (Figure 3a), it becomes evident that several solvents outperform chloroform. For instance, in DMSO equilibrium is reached after only 7 minutes in the presence of TFA (dark blue circles in Figure 3a). Notably, in the absence of TFA, DMSO was not a suitable solvent for the exchange of phenyltrimethoxysilane, contradicting a nucleophile-assisted reaction pathway (grey circles in Figure 3a; see Figure S39 for data on trimethoxysilane ($R = H$)). Other polar solvents such as DMF and acetonitrile also reach equilibrium within one hour, whereas less polar solvents such as dichloromethane, chloroform and benzene fail to reach equilibrium during 60 minutes under these conditions. When plotting the observed conversion after 20 minutes vs. the dielectric

constant of the solvent, a relatively good linear correlation is observed (Figure 3b; see below for a discussion of outliers). These results corroborate the TFA-mediated process predicted by computation (Table 2). Solvation correction by a dielectric continuum model leads to an increase of the barrier of direct MeOH exchange (Table 2, columns 2/3). In contrast, the barriers of TFA-induced exchange are lowered upon solvation correction, or only little effected as in case of the model substrate phenyltrimethoxysilane (Table 2, columns 4/5 and 6/7). These trends agree with the experimental finding that the exchange rate in higher polarity solvents increases if TFA is present, but do not increase in DMSO if TFA is absent (Figure 3).

Interestingly, the solvent polarity seems to not only affect the kinetics of exchange, but also the final equilibrium, as can be seen by the different plateau levels throughout Figure 3a. For instance, a product ratio of 13:35:33:19 ($A_3:A_2B:AB_2:B_3$) was determined in chloroform, whereas a product ratio featuring higher amounts of the twofold- and threefold-exchange products (ratio $A_3:A_2B:AB_2:B_3$: 10:33:37:20) was found in DMSO. This finding supports our proposal that the varying free energies of solvation for methanol vs. ethanol are an important factor governing equilibrium distributions of trialkoxysilane exchange.

Some outliers to the linear trend shown in Figure 3b merit discussion. The first outlier is THF, which should give rise to reasonably fast trialkoxysilane exchange based on its polarity, but instead led to no observable conversion over 60 minutes (Figure 3a). This finding may be explained by the ring-opening polymerization of THF, which can be induced by strong acids.^[96] Even though we found no peaks indicative of such a polymerization by ¹H NMR spectroscopy, we cannot rule out that the occurrence of this side reaction hinders the exchange. The second outlier in respect to the linear polarity trend is pyridine, which leads to a higher conversion than would be expected based on its dielectric constant (Figure 3b). Because pyridine is a reasonably strong Brønsted base, one would expect it to form substantial amounts of the corresponding salt with TFA. This observation suggested a beneficial effect by the presence of a salt (see below). The sigmoidal kinetic curve observed for HMPA as a solvent (Figure 3a) is another unexpected result. Initially, trialkoxysilane exchange is extremely slow, but after an induction period of about 10 minutes surpasses the rate of the more polar solvent acetonitrile. Based on literature precedence,^[97] we propose that HMPA slowly liberates dimethylamine, which like pyridine, forms a salt with TFA that seems to enhance the rate of trialkoxysilane exchange. ¹H NMR monitoring (Figure S40) and a NOESY NMR experiment (Figure S41) show that dimethylamine exchanges with trialkoxysilane, thus forming a $PhSi(OMe)_2(NMe_2)$ intermediate, which appears to increase the reaction rate.

Figure 3. a) Kinetics of representative exchange reaction of phenyltrimethoxysilane with ethanol (100 mol % TFA; solvent as specified in Figure legend; other reaction conditions as specified in the caption of Table 1). b) Correlation between conversion and the dielectric constant (ϵ) of the studied solvents. Conversion is defined as the ratio between the total concentration of EtO–Si and MeO–Si groups, as determined by ¹H NMR integration.

Salts can dramatically increase the exchange rate

The unexpected experimental results pointing toward salt effects (with pyridine and HMPA, see above) prompted us to study a variety of added salts to identify truly mild reaction conditions in chloroform. Two trifluoroacetate (TFA^-) salts with nitrogen-based organic cations dimethylammonium and *N*-methylimidazolium (NMI) and three tetrabutylammonium salts (TBA^+TFA^- , TBA^+TfO^- , $\text{TBA}^+\text{BF}_4^-$) were studied initially. As in the solvent survey, phenyltrimethoxysilane served as the model substrate, because it reacts very slowly in chloroform, even in the presence of 100 mol % TFA (red circles in Figure 4a). The kinetic profiles shown in Figure 4a clearly indicate that salt additives with TFA^- or TfO^- anions enhance the reaction rate. Salts such as $\text{TBA}^+\text{BF}_4^-$ and $\text{TBA}^+\text{PF}_6^-$ (Table S2), enhance the reaction rate to a lesser extent, suggesting that the salt effects reported herein are depending on the charge density and (an)isotropy of both cations and anions.

To probe whether the combination of small, coordinating cations with weakly coordination anions (as in: LiBARf , NaBARf , NMe_4BARf , where $\text{BARf}^- = \text{tetrakis}[3,5\text{-bis}(\text{trifluoromethyl})\text{phenyl}]\text{borate}^{[98,99]}$) can enhance the rate of trialkoxysilane exchange, we studied these salt additives (Figure 4b). Solubility restrictions forced us to use much lower effective salt concentrations (ca. 0.1 mol %). Surprisingly, we found that all BARf salts enhanced the rate of trialkoxysilane exchange significantly compared to the reference reaction with only 100 mol % TFA (in CDCl_3). The differences observed between the three BARf salts are reproducible (Figure S44) and at this small concentration most likely not a consequence of residual water content in the salts.

Finally, when we studied the effect of salts in the absence of TFA (in CDCl_3), thus representing the mildest reaction conditions throughout this study, we found that two trifluoroacetate salts facilitated reasonably fast exchange (Figure 4c). Addition of one equivalent of NMI^+TFA^- and

TBA^+TFA^- led to approximately 18% and 6% conversion after 60 minutes, respectively. The fact that the TBA^+TFA^- salt significantly outcompetes the TBA^+TfO^- salt in the absence of acid (compare Figure 4a with Figure 4c), suggests a specific role that TFA or its conjugate anion play in the direct trialkoxysilane exchange. Notably, NaBARf does not enhance the reaction rate in the absence of TFA. Collectively, our results show that trialkoxysilane exchange can be carried out under surprisingly mild reaction conditions. We made sure that these optimized reaction conditions do not only apply to our model substrate phenyltrimethoxysilane by studying another challenging substrate (*tert*-butyltrimethoxysilane, Figure S45), for which the same trends were observed.

Understanding salt effects by computational chemistry

To scrutinize some of the effects of salt additives, computations were performed in the presence of explicit anions and cations, and the barriers were compared with the additive-free reactions. Due to convergence difficulties on the TFA exchange transition states, the following discussion is narrowed to the MeOH exchange at $\text{PhSi}(\text{OMe})_3$ (Figure 5a/b).^[100] First, the influence of anions was determined by placing TFA^- , OTf^- and BF_4^- nearby the exchanging proton in the transition structure (Figure 5a for TFA^- as an example). Notably, the solvation corrected barrier is lowered only with the TFA^- anion to a significant extent with respect to the additive-free exchange (146 kJ mol^{-1}), while the presence of spherical BF_4^- or more weakly coordinating OTf^- leaves the barrier essentially unchanged (Figure 5a). These results are in agreement with the experimentally observed activity only for TFA^- salts in the absence of acid, and a less pronounced influence of more weakly coordinating anions or with isotropic charge distribution (Figure 4c). The influence of explicit cations was studied by identifying the lowest energy paths for TBA^+ ,

Figure 4. Influence of various salts on the kinetics of the representative exchange reaction of phenyltrimethoxysilane with ethanol (100 mol % TFA unless noted otherwise; solvent CDCl_3 ; other reaction conditions as specified in the caption of Table 1). a) Comparison of salt additives (100 mol %) with larger quaternary ammonium cations and different counterions (in the presence of 100 mol % TFA); b) comparison of salt additives (ca. 0.1 mol %) with small cations and the weakly coordinating BARf counterion (in the presence of 100 mol % TFA), measured in triplicate, data points represent averages of triplicate experiments; c) comparison of salt additives (100 mol %) in the absence of acid. Conversion is defined as the ratio between the total concentration of EtO-Si and MeO-Si groups, as determined by ^1H NMR integration.

Figure 5. Solvation corrected Gibbs free activation energies [kJ mol⁻¹] for a) MeOH-self exchange in the presence of explicit anions, with the TS structure in presence of a trifluoroacetate, b) in the presence of explicit cations, with the TS structure in presence of a sodium cation, c) in the presence of explicit cations with PhSi(OMe)₂TFA, with the TS structure in presence of a lithium cation, d) MeOH-self exchange and TFA-exchange in the presence of an oriented external electric field.

NMe₄⁺, Na⁺, and Li⁺ (Figure 5b for Na⁺ as an example). Interestingly, except for Li⁺, no barrier lowering was observed in the presence of explicit cations. This finding is in agreement with the missing effect of NaBARF in the absence of TFA (Figure 4c). Aiming for an understanding of the pronounced effect of the [M]BARF salts in the presence of TFA (Figure 4b), we computed the barriers for MeOH exchange at the PhSi(OMe)₂(TFA) intermediate (Figure 5c). Interestingly, the barriers for this exchange reaction are not lowered with respect to the additive-free exchange (120 kJ mol⁻¹), but even increased. This is due to substantial stabilization of the starting material through chelation of the small cations (Figure S64). Notably, this stabilization expresses to a lesser extent for the sodium cation, thus explaining the higher reaction rate observed for NaBARF (Figure 4b). Hence, some experimental results remained unexplained, e.g., the observed rate increase with NMe₄BARF, which represents a combination of a weakly coordinating anion (WCA) and a weakly coordinating cation; Figure 4b. We therefore considered general electrostatic effects, such as oriented external electric fields

(OEEF), as responsible. The effect of external electric fields spanned in a specific direction by intramolecular charged units or added salts has been attracting increasing interest.^[101–105] Most notably, the specific consideration of OEEF was identified as key for the understanding of salt additive effects in transition metal catalysis.^[106]

Indeed, computations in an OEEF of 0.01 or 0.02 au field strength had a substantial barrier-lowering effect for all modes, direct exchange, TFA exchange, and MeOH exchange at the PhSi(OMe)₂(TFA) intermediate (Figure 5d). In particular the latter reaction becomes significantly more favourable, providing an explanation of the most pronounced effect of salt additives in the presence of TFA. Hence, although specific effects (e.g. hydrogen bonding with dimethylammonium or NMI⁺, proton shuttling with TFA⁻, etc.) should not be ruled out, part of the observed catalysis may be assigned to electrostatic effects in the aprotic reaction medium. This finding is tantalizing, as it encourages revisiting, e.g., the role of charged additives in silicon polymers or previous interpretations in solvolysis reactions of siloxanes.^[71–74]

Self-assembly of trialkoxysilane cryptates

With insights into the mechanism and the scope of trialkoxysilane exchange in hand, we aimed to exploit the dynamic covalent Si–O bond for the self-assembly of trialkoxysilane cryptates. To this end, we subjected a selection of trimethoxysilanes studied in the kinetic experiments to conditions that represented a compromise between fast trialkoxysilane exchange and an optimal template effect (the latter requirement precludes the use of high polarity solvents such as DMSO).^[78,81] Specifically, we used chloroform as solvent and diethylene glycol (DEG) as a ligand for metal binding and as diol to exchange with the trialkoxysilane. TFA or TfOH were used as acid catalysts (Figure 6), while NaBARF acted as alkali metal template and agent to enhance the rate of the exchange reaction (see above). Molecular sieves (5 Å) served the purpose to keep the reaction medium anhydrous and provide a thermodynamic sink for methanol, which is liberated during self-assembly. To our delight, we were able to isolate four cryptates using this approach: [Na⁺⋯o-Si-(CH₃)₂-1.1.1], [Na⁺⋯o-Si-(C₆H₅)₂-1.1.1], [Na⁺⋯o-Si-(mesityl)₂-1.1.1] and [Na⁺⋯o-Si-(**Bu**)₂-1.1.1] (Figure 6a). Despite our best efforts, the isolated yields were significantly lower than the NMR yields in most cases (73 % vs. 8 %; 58 % vs. 27 %; 58 % vs. 15 %; 47 % vs. 44 %, respectively), indicating that the purification of these compounds is challenging (see below). The low stability of the products towards hydrolysis was deemed the main reason why we could not isolate the other three trialkoxysilane cryptates (R = -H, -CH₂Cl, -C₆F₅) whose synthesis we attempted.

Nevertheless, we were able to obtain single crystals of two cryptates, [Na⁺⋯o-Si-(mesityl)₂-1.1.1] and [Na⁺⋯o-Si-(**Bu**)₂-1.1.1] (Figure 6b), by the layering method (CHCl₃/n-hexane). When inspecting the structural data, the most striking feature of the two trialkoxysilane cryptates is their

Figure 6. a) Metal-templated synthesis of trialkoxysilane cryptates. Reaction conditions: 120 μmol trialkoxysilane, 180 μmol diethylene glycol (DEG), 60.0 μmol NaBARf, 60.0–120 μmol TFA or TfOH in 6 mL anhydrous chloroform or DCM; MS: molecular sieves. Reaction time: 1–15 days. b) Solid state structures of two trialkoxysilane cryptates and one orthoester cryptate as reference (right).^[81] Single crystals were obtained by the layering method ($\text{CHCl}_3/n\text{-hexane}$). Hydrogen atoms and anions are omitted for clarity. Metal ions are displayed at 100% effective ionic radius.^[108]

distorted geometry, which stands in stark contrast to the high symmetry observed in the carbon-based “orthoester” analogue $[\text{Na}^+ \text{C}-\text{o}-(\text{CH}_3)_2-1.1.1]$ (Figure 6b, right hand side). To explain these experimental findings we carried out DFT calculations. Favorable thermodynamics ($\Delta G < -60 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) of cage formation were verified, and only slightly affected by the substituent R on silicon (Table S7). The structural differences between carbon-based orthoester cryptates (i.e. linear) and their silicon analogues reported herein (deformed) do occur also in vacuum optimization, thus ruling out crystal packing effects as the cause for deformed vs. linear arrangement. Evaluations by energy decomposition analyses could not disclose any obvious repulsion effect that is inducing the deformed structure. Instead, we propose the offset arrangement adopted by the silicon derivative to be preferred due to the higher flexibility of valence angle deformation in this third-row element compared to the stiffer T_D coordination at carbon.

For the *i*Bu substituted cryptate as a representative example, we demonstrated that the sodium template can be removed by treating a chloroform solution of $[\text{Na}^+ \text{C}-\text{o}-\text{Si}-(\text{iBu})_2-1.1.1]$ with an anion exchange resin (Lewatit MP68, Cl^- form). The binding constants of the empty cryptand *o*-Si-(*i*Bu)₂-1.1.1 with sodium and lithium ions were determined by NMR titrations whose scope was limited by the solubility of salts. In acetonitrile, moderate binding constants of ca. 50 M^{-1} (NaBARf) and 240 M^{-1} (LiTPFB, where $\text{TPFB}^- = \text{tetrakis(pentafluorophenyl)borate}$) were obtained. The enhanced binding to lithium ions may be due to the distorted geometry of the trialkoxysilane cryptates, which leads to an effectively decreased size of the binding cavity. Such a structural effect was also observed in orthoformate cryptates^[86] and may explain why trialkoxysilane association constants are slightly lower compared to orthoester analogues.^[107] An NMR titration between NaBARf and *o*-Si-(*i*Bu)₂-1.1.1 was also carried out in CDCl_3 . Although the titration was limited by the solubility of the salt, the data

points toward a 2:1 binding stoichiometry in this solvent with the first binding constant in a range that would explain the successful template synthesis ($K_1 = 4500 \text{ M}^{-1}$). Nevertheless, the solid state structures (Figure 6b) demonstrate the formation of an inclusion complex with 1:1 stoichiometry.

Finally, we envisioned the synthesis of mixed trialkoxysilane and orthoester cryptates by carrying out the self-assembly with a 1:1 mixture of trialkoxysilane and orthoester. Unfortunately, these attempts were met with failure, presumably because the difference in reactivity is still too high between the reactive orthoesters and the more inert trialkoxysilanes (despite the rate-enhancing effects of TFA and NaBARf).

Divergent pH-response: trialkoxysilanes hydrolyze at both low and high pH

To assess the stability of the trialkoxysilanes in water, we studied the hydrolysis of model compound phenyltrimethoxysilane ($\text{R} = -\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) under standardized conditions in phosphate buffer solutions of varying pH. The reactions were monitored by ^1H NMR spectroscopy to determine the half-life $t_{1/2}$ and the kinetic rate k_{obs} of the degradation under pseudo first order conditions. As summarized in Table S3, phenyltrimethoxysilane rapidly hydrolyzes under acidic conditions ($t_{1/2} = 2 \text{ min}$ at pH 3.9), but shows a higher stability towards degradation at slightly acidic pH ($t_{1/2} = 64 \text{ min}$ at pH 5.7). Contrary to carbon-based orthoesters, which are stable at basic pH,^[86] the trialkoxysilane was also found to hydrolyze rapidly under basic conditions ($t_{1/2} = 4 \text{ min}$ at pH 8.7). Analysis by ^1H NMR spectroscopy indicates that hydrolysis under acidic and basic conditions lead to condensation of silanetriols and to the formation of polymeric siloxanes. This finding explains the difficulties encountered during the isolation of the trialkoxysilane

Figure 7. Comparison of half-lives $t_{1/2}$ for the hydrolysis of phenyltrimethoxysilane (red) and trimethyl orthoacetate^[86] (blue) in buffered media. Error bars correspond to 95% confidence interval (experiments performed in triplicate).

cryptates. Because their degradation by hydrolysis cannot be minimized by quench with acid or base, the isolation of these compounds is like “dancing on a volcano” (the volcano plot shown in Figure 7 serves to illustrate this point).

While this divergent pH-response is a challenge for researchers seeking to isolate discrete compounds (see above), it could offer unique advantages for the use of trialkoxysilane-based stimuli-responsive gels, polymers and colloids as drug delivery systems for the selective transport or release of encapsulated or preloaded drugs in either acidic (stomach, cancer cells, lysosome) or basic (intestine, mitochondria) medium.

Conclusion

The present work provides a comprehensive experimental and theoretical study of substrate, reagent and environmental effects on the alcohol exchange rates of trialkoxysilanes. By judicious choice of the reaction conditions, an otherwise negligible exchange reaction can be accelerated by orders of magnitude. Experimental observations and theoretical analyses reveal and rationalize solvent polarity, specific salt effects and external electric fields imposed by the ion pairs as viable to enhance the exchange rate. The ability to control trialkoxysilane exchange with diverse reagents makes this reaction an attractive tool for the generation of complex reaction networks and the synthesis of stimuli-responsive materials. Our mechanistic insights are relevant for diverse research communities, because the Si–O bond is ubiquitous in the geosphere and in functional materials.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DE1830/2-1, GR5007/2-1) and the European Union (ERCstg 802428 “SUPRANET”, ERCstg 948708

“pCx4All”). The authors acknowledge support by the state of Baden-Württemberg through bwHPC and the German Research Foundation (DFG) through grant no INST 40/575-1 FUGG (JUSTUS 2 cluster). Markus Hecht and Sarah Spiewok are acknowledged for substrate syntheses. Oleg Borodin is acknowledged for assistance with crystallographic refinement. Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the Supporting Information of this article.

Keywords: Alkoxysilanes · Computational Chemistry · Dynamic Covalent Chemistry · Host-Guest Chemistry · Salt Effects

- [1] S. Ulrich, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2019**, *52*, 510–519.
- [2] X. Xin, Z. Zhang, X. Zhang, J. Chen, X. Lin, P. Sun, X. Liu, *Nanoscale* **2021**, *13*, 11712–11733.
- [3] M. M. Zegota, M. A. Müller, B. Lantzberg, G. Kizilsavas, J. A. S. Coelho, P. Moscariello, M. Martínez-Negro, S. Morsbach, P. M. P. Gois, M. Wagner, D. Y. W. Ng, S. L. Kuan, T. Weil, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2021**, *143*, 17047–17058.
- [4] M. M. Zegota, T. Wang, C. Seidler, D. Y. Wah Ng, S. L. Kuan, T. Weil, *Bioconjugate Chem.* **2018**, *29*, 2665–2670.
- [5] M. J. Swierczynski, Y. Ding, Z. T. Ball, *Bioconjugate Chem.* **2022**, *33*, 2307–2313.
- [6] J. Xia, P. Zhao, K. Zheng, C. Lu, S. Yin, H. Xu, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58*, 542–546.
- [7] F. Lu, H. Zhang, W. Pan, N. Li, B. Tang, *Chem. Commun.* **2021**, *57*, 7067–7082.
- [8] D. K. Kölmel, E. T. Kool, *Chem. Rev.* **2017**, *117*, 10358–10376.
- [9] K. L. Diehl, I. V. Kolesnichenko, S. A. Robotham, J. L. Bachman, Y. Zhong, J. S. Brodbelt, E. V. Anslyn, *Nat. Chem.* **2016**, *8*, 968–973.
- [10] O. Borodin, Y. Shchukin, C. C. Robertson, S. Richter, M. von Delius, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2021**, *143*, 16448–16457.
- [11] J. Li, P. Nowak, S. Otto, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2013**, *135*, 9222–9239.
- [12] H. Xie, T. J. Finnegan, V. W. Liyana Gunawardana, R. Z. Pavlović, C. E. Moore, J. D. Badjić, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2021**, *143*, 3874–3880.
- [13] J. Yu, M. Gaedke, F. Schaufelberger, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2023**, *26*, e202201130.
- [14] N. Ponnuswamy, F. B. L. Cougnon, J. M. Clough, G. D. Pantoş, J. K. M. Sanders, *Science* **2012**, *338*, 783–785.
- [15] S. P. Black, K. M. Sanders, A. R. Stefankiewicz, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2014**, *43*, 1861–1872.
- [16] R. Gu, J. M. Lehn, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2021**, *143*, 14136–14146.
- [17] H. V. Schröder, Y. Zhang, A. J. Link, *Nat. Chem.* **2021**, *13*, 850–857.
- [18] X. Zhang, K. Liu, J. Zhao, Z. Zhang, Z. Luo, Y. Guo, H. Zhang, Y. Wang, R. Bai, D. Zhao, X. Yang, Y. Liu, X. Yan, J. *Am. Chem. Soc.* **2022**, *144*, 11434–11443.

- [19] Y. Tian, Y. Guo, X. Dong, X. Wan, K. Cheng, R. Chang, S. Li, X. Cao, Y. Chan, A. C. Sue, *Nat. Synth.* **2023**, *2*, 395–402.
- [20] C. M. McHale, L. J. Karas, X. Wang, J. I. Wu, O. S. Miljanić, *Org. Lett.* **2021**, *23*, 2253–2257.
- [21] C. G. Pappas, P. K. Mandal, B. Liu, B. Kauffmann, X. Miao, D. Komáromy, W. Hoffmann, C. Manz, R. Chang, K. Liu, K. Pagel, I. Huc, S. Otto, *Nat. Chem.* **2020**, *12*, 1180–1186.
- [22] Y. Jin, Q. Wang, P. Taynton, W. Zhang, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2014**, *47*, 1575–1586.
- [23] E. Moulin, G. Cormos, N. Giuseppone, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2012**, *41*, 1031–1049.
- [24] T. Kunde, T. Pausch, B. M. Schmidt, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2021**, 5844–5856.
- [25] T. Hasell, A. I. Cooper, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **2016**, *1*, 16053.
- [26] F. Haase, B. V. Lotsch, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2020**, *49*, 8469–8500.
- [27] L. Ma, C. J. E. Haynes, A. B. Grommet, A. Walczak, C. C. Parkins, C. M. Doherty, L. Longley, A. Tron, A. R. Stefankiewicz, T. D. Bennett, J. R. Nitschke, *Nat. Chem.* **2020**, *12*, 270–275.
- [28] B. Qin, S. Liu, Z. Huang, L. Zeng, J. F. Xu, X. Zhang, *Nat. Commun.* **2022**, *13*, 7595.
- [29] Z. Zhang, D. Lei, C. Zhang, Z. Wang, Y. Jin, W. Zhang, X. Liu, J. Sun, *Adv. Mater.* **2023**, *35*, 2208619.
- [30] P. Chakma, D. Konkolewicz, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58*, 9682–9695.
- [31] H. Vardhan, A. Nafady, A. M. Al-Enizi, S. Ma, *Nanoscale* **2019**, *11*, 21679–21708.
- [32] X. Li, H. Wang, H. Chen, Q. Zheng, Q. Zhang, H. Mao, Y. Liu, S. Cai, B. Sun, C. Dun, M. P. Gordon, H. Zheng, J. A. Reimer, J. J. Urban, J. Ciston, T. Tan, E. M. Chan, J. Zhang, Y. Liu, *Chem* **2020**, *6*, 933–944.
- [33] Y. Gu, J. Zhao, J. A. Johnson, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2020**, *59*, 5022–5049.
- [34] F. Beuerle, B. Gole, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2018**, *57*, 4850–4878.
- [35] M. Mastalerz, *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2018**, *51*, 2411–2422.
- [36] *Dynamic Covalent Chemistry: Principles, Reactions, and Applications* (Eds.: W. Zhang, Y. Jin), Wiley, Chichester, **2018**.
- [37] P. T. Corbett, J. Leclaire, L. Vial, K. R. West, J. Wietor, J. K. M. Sanders, S. Otto, *Chem. Rev.* **2006**, *106*, 3652–3711.
- [38] S. Ji, W. Cao, Y. Yu, H. Xu, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2014**, *53*, 6781–6785.
- [39] B. Rasmussen, A. Sørensen, H. Gotfredsen, M. Pittelkow, *Chem. Commun.* **2014**, *50*, 3716–3718.
- [40] T. Santos, D. S. Rivero, Y. Pérez-Pérez, E. Martín-Encinas, J. Pasán, A. H. Daranas, R. Carrillo, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2021**, *60*, 18783–18791.
- [41] D. S. Rivero, R. E. Paiva-Feener, T. Santos, E. Martín-Encinas, R. Carrillo, *Macromolecules* **2021**, *54*, 10428–10434.
- [42] Z. Lei, H. Chen, C. Luo, Y. Rong, Y. Hu, Y. Jin, R. Long, K. Yu, W. Zhang, *Nat. Chem.* **2022**, *14*, 1399–1404.
- [43] M. Liu, L. Guo, S. Jin, B. Tan, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2019**, *7*, 5153–5172.
- [44] J. M. García, G. O. Jones, K. Virwani, B. D. McCloskey, D. J. Boday, G. M. Huurne, H. W. Horn, D. J. Coady, A. M. Bintaleb, A. M. S. Alabulrahman, F. Alsewailam, H. A. A. Almegren, J. L. Hedrick, *Science* **2014**, *344*, 732–735.
- [45] Y. Zhou, Y. Yuan, L. You, E. V. Anslyn, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2015**, *21*, 8207–8213.
- [46] L. R. Sutton, W. A. Donaubauer, F. Hampel, A. Hirsch, *Chem. Commun.* **2004**, 1758–1759.
- [47] A. G. Orrillo, A. M. Escalante, R. L. E. Furlan, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2016**, *22*, 6746–6749.
- [48] R. C. Brachvogel, M. von Delius, *Chem. Sci.* **2015**, *6*, 1399–1403.
- [49] R. C. Brachvogel, M. von Delius, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* **2016**, *22*, 3662–3670.
- [50] M. Bothe, A. G. Orrillo, R. L. E. Furlan, M. von Delius, *Synlett* **2019**, *30*, 1988–1994.
- [51] M. D. Capela, N. J. Mosey, L. Xing, R. Wang, A. Petitjean, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2011**, *17*, 4598–4612.
- [52] O. Borodin, Y. Shchukin, J. Schmid, M. von Delius, *Chem. Commun.* **2022**, 58, 10178–10181.
- [53] J. Heppekausen, R. Stade, R. Goddard, A. Fürstner, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2010**, *132*, 11045–11057.
- [54] Y. Hu, C. Wu, Q. Pan, Y. Jin, R. Lyu, V. Martinez, S. Huang, J. Wu, L. J. Wayment, N. A. Clark, M. B. Raschke, Y. Zhao, W. Zhang, *Nat. Synth.* **2022**, *1*, 449–454.
- [55] H. Ying, Y. Zhang, J. Cheng, *Nat. Commun.* **2014**, *5*, 3218.
- [56] A. E. Dascalu, L. Halgreen, A. Torres-Huerta, H. Valkenier, *Chem. Commun.* **2022**, 58, 11103–11106.
- [57] S. E. Eldred, D. A. Stone, S. H. Gellman, S. S. Stahl, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2003**, *125*, 3422–3423.
- [58] Y. Ruff, V. Garavini, N. Giuseppone, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2014**, *136*, 6333–6339.
- [59] B. M. Matysiak, G. Monreal Santiago, S. Otto, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2022**, *28*, e202201043.
- [60] J. Roesser, D. Prill, M. J. Bojdys, P. Fayon, A. Trewin, A. N. Fitch, M. U. Schmidt, A. Thomas, *Nat. Chem.* **2017**, *9*, 977–982.
- [61] C. A. Tretbar, J. A. Neal, Z. Guan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141*, 16595–16599.
- [62] C. von Hänisch, O. Hampe, F. Weigend, S. Stahl, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2007**, *46*, 4775–4779.
- [63] F. Dankert, R. M. Richter, F. Weigend, X. Xie, M. Balmer, C. von Hänisch, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2021**, *60*, 10393–10401.
- [64] J. S. Ritch, T. Chivers, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2007**, *46*, 4610–4613.
- [65] K. E. L. Husted, C. M. Brown, P. Shieh, I. Kevlishvili, S. L. Kristufek, H. Zafar, J. V. Accardo, J. C. Cooper, R. S. Klausen, H. J. Kulik, J. S. Moore, N. R. Sottos, J. A. Kalow, J. A. Johnson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2023**, *145*, 1916–1923.
- [66] D. Hartmann, L. Greb, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2020**, *59*, 22510–22513.
- [67] M. O. Saed, E. M. Terentjev, *Sci. Rep.* **2020**, *10*, 17–19.
- [68] T. Debsharma, V. Amfilochiou, A. A. Wróblewska, I. De Baere, W. Van Paeppegem, F. E. Du Prez, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2022**, *144*, 12280–12289.
- [69] D. Khedaoui, C. Tribout, J. Bratananu, F. D'Agosto, C. Boisson, D. Montarnal, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2023**, *62*, e202300225.
- [70] C. Tretbar, J. Castro, K. Yokoyama, Z. Guan, *ChemRxiv* **2023**, <https://doi.org/10.26434/chemrxiv-2023-vqxvm>.
- [71] C. G. Swain, K.-R. Poerschke, W. Ahmed, R. L. Schowen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1974**, *96*, 4700–4702.
- [72] P. E. Dietze, J. Khattak, E. Fickus, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **1991**, *32*, 307–310.
- [73] D. J. Oostendorp, G. L. Bertrand, J. O. Stoffer, *J. Adhes. Sci. Technol.* **1992**, *6*, 171–191.
- [74] P. E. Dietze, *J. Org. Chem.* **1993**, *58*, 5653–5662.
- [75] N. Ansmann, D. Hartmann, S. Sailer, P. Erdmann, R. Maskey, M. Schorpp, L. Greb, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2022**, *61*, e202203947.
- [76] D. Hartmann, T. Thorwart, R. Müller, J. Thusek, J. Schwabedissen, A. Mix, J. H. Lamm, B. Neumann, N. W. Mitzel, L. Greb, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2021**, *143*, 18784–18793.
- [77] R. Maskey, T. Thorwart, S. Ebel, A. Jovic, D. Hartmann, L. Greb, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2023**, *29*, e202300269.
- [78] S. Hollstein, O. Shyshov, M. Hanževački, J. Zhao, T. Rudolf, C. M. Jäger, M. von Delius, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2022**, *61*, e202201831.

- [79] X. Wang, O. Shyshov, M. Hanževački, C. M. Jäger, M. von Delius, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141*, 8868–8876.
- [80] H. Löw, E. Mena-Osteritz, M. von Delius, *Chem. Commun.* **2019**, *55*, 11434–11437.
- [81] R. C. Brachvogel, F. Hampel, M. von Delius, *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, *6*, 7129.
- [82] O. Shyshov, R. C. Brachvogel, T. Bachmann, R. Srikantharajah, D. Segets, F. Hampel, R. Puchta, M. von Delius, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2017**, *56*, 776–781.
- [83] CDCl₃ was stored over 3 Å MS to ensure anhydrous conditions, and K₂CO₃ to quench residual acid.
- [84] D. Datta, *J. Phys. Org. Chem.* **1991**, *4*, 96–100.
- [85] E. V. Anslyn, D. A. Dougherty, *Modern Physical Organic Chemistry*, University Science Books, Sausalito, **2006**.
- [86] H. Löw, E. Mena-Osteritz, M. von Delius, *Chem. Sci.* **2018**, *9*, 4785–4793.
- [87] R. R. Holmes, *Chem. Rev.* **1990**, *90*, 17–31.
- [88] A. P. Bento, F. M. Bickelhaupt, *J. Org. Chem.* **2007**, *72*, 2201–2207.
- [89] J. P. Wagner, P. R. Schreiner, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2015**, *54*, 12274–12296.
- [90] S. Okumoto, N. Fujita, S. Yamabe, *J. Phys. Chem. A* **1998**, *102*, 3991–3998.
- [91] M. Cypryk, Y. Apeloig, *Organometallics* **2002**, *21*, 2165–2175.
- [92] M. Ciaccia, S. Di Stefano, *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2015**, *13*, 646–654.
- [93] M. Ciaccia, R. Cacciapaglia, P. Mencarelli, L. Mandolini, S. Di Stefano, *Chem. Sci.* **2013**, *4*, 2253–2261.
- [94] A. R. Bassindale, T. Stout, *J. Organomet. Chem.* **1984**, *271*, C1–C3.
- [95] W. Uhlig, A. Tzschach, *J. Organomet. Chem.* **1989**, *378*, C1–C5.
- [96] G. Pruckmayr, T. K. Wu, *Macromolecules* **1978**, *11*, 662–668.
- [97] K. B. Dillon, N. D. A. H. Khabbass, C. J. Ludman, *Polyhedron* **1989**, *8*, 2623–2626.
- [98] I. Krossing, I. Raabe, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2004**, *43*, 2066–2090.
- [99] I. M. Riddlestone, A. Kraft, J. Schaefer, I. Krossing, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2018**, *57*, 13982–14024.
- [100] Explicit computation of both anion and cation did not produce stable results, since charged species tend to aggregate during structural optimization and escape the secondary sphere of the reactants.
- [101] S. Shaik, D. Mandal, R. Ramanan, *Nat. Chem.* **2016**, *8*, 1091–1098.
- [102] S. Ciampi, N. Darwish, H. M. Aitken, I. Díez-Perez, M. L. Coote, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2018**, *47*, 5146–5164.
- [103] V. V. Welborn, L. Ruiz Pestana, T. Head-Gordon, *Nat. Catal.* **2018**, *1*, 649–655.
- [104] S. Shaik, D. Danovich, J. Joy, Z. Wang, T. Stuyver, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2020**, *142*, 12551–12562.
- [105] C. Zheng, Y. Mao, J. Kozuch, A. O. Atsango, Z. Ji, T. E. Markland, S. G. Boxer, *Nat. Chem.* **2022**, *14*, 891–897.
- [106] J. Joy, T. Stuyver, S. Shaik, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2020**, *142*, 3836–3850.
- [107] R.-C. Brachvogel, H. Maid, M. von Delius, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **2015**, *16*, 20641–20656.
- [108] R. D. Shannon, *Acta Crystallogr. Sect. A* **1976**, *32*, 751–767.

Manuscript received: March 21, 2023

Accepted manuscript online: April 28, 2023

Version of record online: ■■■, ■■■

Research Articles

Supramolecular Chemistry

S. Hollstein, P. Erdmann, A. Ulmer, H. Löw,
L. Greb,* M. von Delius* — e202304083

Trialkoxysilane Exchange: Scope, Mechanism, Cryptates and pH-Response

The exchange reaction of trialkoxysilanes with alcohols typically requires very harsh conditions and has therefore not been used for the self-assembly of host-guest systems. In this work, unexpected solvent and salt effects are described, rationalized and exploited for the synthesis of degradable supramolecular hosts.